

THE IMPORTANCE AND ROLE OF SPORT IN HIGHER EDUCATION
ЗНАЧЕНИЕ И РОЛЬ СПОРТА В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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Аннотация. Настоящая статья посвящена актуальной проблеме физической подготовки в процессе получения высшего образования. В работе анализируются особенности подготовки студентов данной категории обучения, рассмотрены пути преодоления отдельных проблем, возникающих в ходе физической подготовки.

Abstract. This article is devoted to the actual problem of physical training in the process of obtaining higher education. The paper analyzes the features of training students in this category of training, considers ways to overcome certain problems that arise during physical training.

Ключевые слова: физическая подготовка, высшее образование, спорт, социология спорта.

Keywords: physical training, higher education, sports, sociology of sports.

The sport of higher achievements is organically connected with mass sports, although this connection is not enclosed in the rigid framework of mathematical relations. It is impossible to deduce, say, from every hundred (thousand) people involved in sports, certainly a certain, and even more so a constant number of people in big sports - too many factors affect this ratio. These include the selection methodology, the degree of actual readiness of the coaching staff for a certain type and level of activity, the provision of bases, inventory and equipment, the number and nature of devices and simulators, the

value orientations of children and parents, the attitude of the administration, the actual state of the management system, the organization and many other factors.

Sport is also one of the most important means of reasonable use of free time, which, according to K. Marx, is a true measure of the wealth of society, since it is here that the human personality is recreated, its bright individual uniqueness.

The importance of sport in life is multifaceted, and there is no need to talk about many of its well-known functions. However, it is illegal to assign functions unusual for sport or to solve some complex social tasks with its help. For example, it cannot solve the problem of social contradictions and inequality in capitalist society, although it is widely used as one of the effective means of diverting the attention of workers from the political struggle. By itself, sport does not "deform" a person and does not revive "aggressive instincts", as some bourgeois sociologists believe. But attempts to "channel" these "aggressive instincts" through sport are characteristic of modern capitalist society.

Physical education at the university is a learning process in the interests of preparing students for active social life and fruitful work, as well as preserving and strengthening health, continuous improvement of physical, moral, intellectual, aesthetic education of the individual, including all types and forms of organizational, purposeful and systematic activities carried out by state and private educational institutions in order to acquire vital physical qualities and sports improvement of students.

The problem of human health is one of the most complex and urgent in the first half of the twentieth century, I. I. Brekhman introduces a special concept of "valeology", which he proposes to name a new science of human health. Valeology rightfully refers it to those modern problems that are commonly called global.

Valeology is not only a science, but also a lifestyle; it is the art of life and survival. In the animal world, survival is associated with adaptation. A person survives in the world not so much through adaptation, but through the transformation of the world, through the creation of such models of the world in which his connection with existence must be present. F. A. Kashapov, O. V. Terentyev, V. E. Zeissler emphasize that only connection with existence makes a person adapted to the world, socialized and socially healthy. V. P. Kaznacheev reveals the essential links between human health and public health, on the one hand, and education, on the other. Indicates the importance of medical, pedagogical and

physical education knowledge to achieve a comprehensive effect of human health and society

One of the most important tasks that human sciences should solve is the development of the problem of health as a fundamental right and a special value of the personality of modern civilization. Human health in the system of his worldview values is the most important personal guideline, since it acts as a condition for the realization of a person's creative potential. But, as you know, within the framework of valeology, the goal of strengthening the health of the human body and its psycho-emotional health is not set. Here we are talking only about improving the general humanitarian culture of a person. The introduction of humanitarian values into the system of strengthening spiritual health is the prerogative of the valeological approach in education. The formation of a responsible attitude to one's own health also depends on a reasonable and spiritual attitude of the individual to the world and to himself.

Spiritual health is a necessary condition for a person's self-realization. And at the same time, it determines the awareness of the realization of one's potential and in this sense significantly affects the level of physical health. Spiritual health expresses a state of subjective well-being, which reflects a positive emotional self-assessment of one's life. The health of an individual is measured by the level of well-being of the social structure of society.

At the same time, health is a "good" achieved by the individual's own efforts. A person largely becomes the subject of his own health. It depends on the will of a person what he is able to create in himself and around him, as well as how he will use the techniques of producing health. The philosophy of health proceeds from the attitude about the complex nature of health, takes into account the social and personal aspects of the formation of the need for health. If an individual's social health is determined by the level of his well-being in a particular social system, then individual health is determined by the ability to independently control his behavior, the process of self-development and take responsibility for his health

Health in the physical aspect is an integral part of a person's social health. Physical health is a complex activity:

- 1) pedagogical (coaching);
- 2) health-improving (restorative, medical-preventive and hygienic),
- 3) specifically physical education and health and mass sports, developing the body and soul with the help of special complexes of physical activity.

Health in the physical education aspect should be highlighted, since there is a unique specific method of its formation - achieving, strengthening and developing health with the help of special sets of physical exercises and movements in physical culture and health practices and in various sports, as a result of which not only the body is transformed, but also the psychospiritual essence of man.

The authors believe, and we agree with them, that health in the physical education and sports aspect can be considered as a special form and way of achieving, strengthening and developing health with the help of special physical education and sports training types of physical activity. These movements constitute the main content of physical education and health practices and various sports. They generally beneficially transform the body and soul of a person. These issues at the Altai State Medical University, in the theory and practice of physical education, are dealt with by teachers of the department of physical education and healthy lifestyle under the leadership of the head of the department V.P. Vorontsova.

Now we can consistently move on to physical culture and sports as applied methods of developing and strengthening a person's psychophysical health. Physical culture is an integral part of the general culture of society. It is aimed at strengthening health, developing the physical, moral-volitional and intellectual abilities of a person with the goal of harmonious formation of his personality. Physical culture is an effective way to increase people's social and labor activity. It is capable of satisfying a number of important moral, aesthetic and creative needs, the vital needs of mutual communication and the development of friendly relations between peoples and countries.

Sport is an organic part of physical culture. It represents a special area of competition between people and their communities for comparing the achievements of athletes in certain types of physical exercise, technical, intellectual and other forms of training. Student sports includes general developmental classes, special training in sports sections and teams, collective and organizational work in sports-oriented public associations (sports clubs, physical education groups, etc.), and participation in sports competitions.

It is worth noting that student sports life covers not only young people with a sufficient level of health, but also students with physical disabilities or who, for one reason or another, experience certain physical difficulties, including addictive behavior.

For such groups of youth, special training is organized, which is carried out in special health-improving medical groups or in special sports institutions for the disabled, at the expense of the institution and social protection authorities.

Now let's turn to the practical form of physical education and sports activities represented by tourism.

Tourism is a special applied (practical) means of physical education and a sport. Thanks to it, on the one hand, one's own physical and psycho-spiritual health is strengthened, and on the other hand, one communicates with the beauty of nature and develops the ability to overcome the difficulties of being in difficult natural conditions by developing character and willpower. Sports training for tourists includes motor actions of various form and content, associated with deliberate overcoming of significant distances in sparsely populated areas, performed in natural conditions by collective efforts.

The purpose of such physical and psycho-spiritual stress is to develop in a person the skills and abilities he needs in production, military and everyday activities, while simultaneously solving educational, educational, health and sports problems.

In addition, active tourism, which is both a sport and a method of active recreation, and "nature-appropriate" behavior.

They are also associated with fulfilling the mandatory requirements of overcoming routes on hikes, with increasing complexity (route category), in accordance with the Unified All-Union Sports Classification. This increase in effort and skill makes it possible to improve a person's physical, mental, collectivist and organizational abilities.

Educational, educational, health and sports tasks in tourism belong to the category of general tasks. Their solution is carried out interconnectedly and generally does not depend on the age and degree of special physical fitness of those involved. For example, during a hike, educational tasks can be solved by direct influence on each participant from the team, and individual members of the group - on the entire group. As a result, a sense of collectivism is formed and personal interests are subordinated to public ones. And the duration of movement in traveling conditions, a gradual increase in physical activity develops the endurance, strong-willed and collectivistic qualities of the participants in the hike.

Simultaneously with the educational tasks during the campaign, educational ones are also solved. Knowledge of local history, natural history, and

topography, obtained by those studying in theory, is accumulated and consolidated even before the hike. Here the theory is supported by practice. In camping conditions, knowledge of the methods of developing motor skills and abilities is also improved.

Thus, physical education for students in higher educational institutions has a program that allows students to develop and strengthen their health, both physically and spiritually.

Students have the opportunity to take part in various competitions, both within their university and inter-university, at different levels, from city to all-Russian. This fosters team spirit, willpower and other important qualities for a person.

Thus, we can say that physical education plays an important role for students. It not only shapes physical culture, but also the humanistic values of sports and a healthy lifestyle. In practice, the possibilities of the positive impact of physical culture and sports on physical (somatic) health, on the spiritual world, on the will and on the moral principles of a young person's personality are realized. Physical education and sports activity is increasingly emerging as a means of improving the quality of life, as a form of creativity, as the creative force of sport, not only in general, but also for oneself personally.

So, having examined the social essence of sport, we can state that sport is characterized by creative activity associated with a person's knowledge of his capabilities, along with the search for ways to realize the growing abilities of people to the maximum. This function of physical culture and sports is most manifested in the league of highest achievements, because on the way to the coveted pedestal, the athlete is forced to continuously improve the training system, search for the latest means and methods of training, come up with new technical elements and find innovative solutions for conducting direct sports activities. Each athlete needs to strive for maximum realization of their own potential and their capabilities, to use them as effectively as possible in the stages of preparation for competitions, in order to climb higher and higher on the ladder of sports excellence.

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